

Towards a Framework for Trust in Clinical AI: Expanding the Unit of Analysis

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From diagnosis to patient scheduling, AI is being considered across different clinical applications. Despite increasingly powerful clinical AI, uptake into actual clinical workflows remains limited. One of the major challenges is developing appropriate trust with clinicians. In this paper, we investigate trust in clinical AI in a wider perspective beyond the user's interactions with the AI. We offer several points in the clinical AI development, usage, and monitoring process that can have a significant impact on the clinician's trust. Future work will look at how these points affect trust and how to calibrate trust at these different points.

CCS CONCEPTS •**Human-centered computing~Human computer interaction (HCI)~HCI theory, concepts and models**

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1 INTRODUCTION

AI is increasingly being considered across different healthcare areas: from patient facing applications to clinical workflow enhancements [14, 69]. AI can enable healthcare providers towards realizing what’s known as the “quadruple aim”: improved patient experience, better health outcomes, improved staff experience, and lower cost of care [7]. AI has the potential to give doctors more time in engaging with patients by taking care of the menial, non-critical tasks [68, 71, 74]. The promise of AI for healthcare is rife with hype, with many machine learning models outperforming clinician performance in diagnosis in controlled settings, spiking some concerns of professional autonomy among clinicians [25, 27, 54, 64, 71].

The major focus of the AI community has been on crafting better performing models, rather than the effects of AI implementation in the wild and challenges associated with adoption [63, 66]. Despite ever better AI models, the adoption of AI into actual clinical practice is limited [74]. Trust remains a critical challenge in deploying clinical AI, being influenced by many factors (user education, experience, bias, system controllability, complexity, risks, etc.) [2, 5]. Even if the AI system is deployed into an existing workflow, whether the clinician trusts it enough to adopt in usage remains a challenge [31].

Research investigating how trust is formed in clinical AI in the wild is lacking. Many studies investigating trust in AI-assisted decision making do not go beyond evaluations of the AI’s UI in a laboratory setting (often focused on XAI). Vereschak et al., in a systematic review of methodologies to study trust in AI-assisted decision making, call for better methods to investigate trust that are more ecologically sound [70]. Similarly, in a survey of AI-decision making research, Lai et al. call for more investigations of AI beyond discrete, laboratory trials [39].

This paper makes two contributions: an expansion of the unit of analysis of trust in clinical AI beyond XAI and a review of relevant points of analysis within the clinical AI development process. The distributed processes of trusting within clinical AI are rendered as points of investigation for future work.

2 EXPANDING TRUST

Trust is a multifaceted, multidisciplinary, and challenging theoretical concept to study and define, with many definitions from different fields abounding [42, 48, 60]. Despite this, there are some common, important considerations that bind them. To define trust, we follow Vereschak et al.’s systematic review of trust definitions within Human-AI literature [70]. They cement Lee and See’s seminal definition of trust as compromising all the relevant elements of trust (vulnerability, positive expectations, and trust rendered as an attitude). Trust is “the attitude that an agent will help achieve an individual’s goals in a situation characterized by uncertainty and vulnerability” [42, 70].

In an integration of empirical research on trust, Hoff and Bashir build upon three variables of trust: dispositional, situational, and learned trust [31, 50]. They render trust as being influenced by multiple factors: culture, age, personality, type of system used, difficulty of the task, workload, team dynamic, decisional freedom, etc. Similarly, Chiou and Lee advocate for a broader analysis of trust to encompass the sociotechnical aspects of trusting [13]. In recent work on human-robot teaming, Huang et al. define a Distributed Dynamic Team Trust (D2T2) model, establishing trust as “a distributed, networked state that is constantly in flux” [32]. This framework includes interpersonal and technical factors that relate to trust in a dynamic, transitive light. In other work, de Visser et al. emphasize the longitudinal, relationship-like nature of trust, offering methods for trust dampening and repairing [16, 17].

These directions in trust research offer potential expansions of our current research of trust in clinical AI. There is an expansion of the unit of analysis beyond the individual and AI at one moment in time. As Möllering argues, “people’s trust should be conceptualized and operationalized as a continuous process of forming and reforming the attitudes static surveys

have measured so far and, crucially, as part of larger social processes” [53]. What’s often missing in investigations of trust in clinical AI is the cultural and organizational processes in which clinical AI is implemented. Integrating AI into a clinical workflow involves a complex web of stakeholders and processes [18]. Instead, studies tend to focus on individual interactions of a clinician and a prototype. While these investigations are valuable, they dodge the larger picture of how trusting occurs. The process of trusting spans longer time horizons, distributed across time, material, and social worlds. In the next section, we’ll use recent work in deploying clinical AI to showcase this.

3 EXPANDING THE UNIT OF ANALYSIS OF TRUST IN CLINICAL AI

Much of the research on trust in clinical AI focuses on measures of trust during the initial interaction with a prototype, often through some representation of XAI [29, 61]. Rarely is the case of trust before the prototype considered crucial [63]. However, as evidenced by studies from practitioners developing clinical AI, the process of trusting begins way before clinicians ever see an interface. We need to investigate trust in clinical AI beyond what is most apt to the domain of HCI and instead consider the larger complexities of integrating into a clinical environment. We’ll consider 4 areas of trust development: pre-development, during development, during usage, and during monitoring.

3.1 Pre-Development

3.1.1 Personal Differences in How Clinicians Trust

Even before AI development begins, trust formation can occur. People have different inclinations to trust, often known as dispositional trust [6, 31, 67]. Culture, age, attachment styles, and other personal differences all count towards this dispositional trust [26, 31]. These differences can greatly affect trust and reliance in ways not related to the properties of the AI [42]. Henry et al. found that provider characteristics were closely associated with the likelihood of evaluating an alert from clinical AI: those who have used it before we’re more likely to use it again [30]. Clinicians may have positive expectations (or lack thereof) in clinical AI, informed by their past experiences, culture, expertise, gossip, relevant industry news, mental models, affect etc. [6, 12, 70]. These differences are rarely considered when investigating trust in clinical AI, despite having important implications for how to calibrate appropriate trust.

3.2 During Development

3.2.1 Trust Through the AI Development Team

Trust also develops during the development of the AI, starting as early as the assembling of the team developing the AI. Releasing clinical AI is an extensive, complex process [15, 18]. The development team having the right professional credibility and experience to engage in this process indicates positive expectations being formed: that a negative outcome will be unlikely with these stakeholders [44, 56]. Clinicians may trust an AI simply because they value the brand based on prior experiences or cultural approval of a brand.

3.2.2 Trust Through the Training of the AI

Once the development of the AI begins, the training the selection of the AI’s dataset, training, and metrics influence trust [72]. Reviewing the inputs of the AI with clinicians can help foster trust and catch quality issues [6]. Cai et al. note that some pathologists wanted to know the “quantity and diversity of the training data” to understand the generalizability and capacities of the AI within the clinician’s local context [10]. Pathologists wouldn’t trust the AI unless it were trained on

judgements made by well-respected clinicians [10]. Pathologists insisted on knowing “a summary of the volume and types of clinical cases that the algorithm was created from” and “from diverse sources would be more representative” [10].

3.2.3 Trust Through Clinical Involvement

The degree of clinical involvement has an impact on trust in several ways [6]. Firstly, the better the development team’s understanding of the clinical context, the better the outcome will be for integration into the workflow, the better their understanding of clinician’s mental models, and thus, higher positive expectations from the clinical team [13, 33, 40]. Cai et al. found that dissimilar mental models between pathologists and the AI system degraded trust [9].

Secondly, more clinical involvement means clinicians will have more of a stake in designing the task allocation or division of labor of the AI [33, 47]. As a side effect of these sessions, the clinical team can further understand the purpose of the AI, how to use it, and its limitations by being active participants in the design process. They can start to calibrate their trust in the AI before any actual performance with it and prevent misuse [6, 42].

Lastly, the AI team will be able to develop relationships with the clinical team. Sendak et al. offer us a profound insight: “trust in a technology is rooted in relationships - not in a technical specification or feature” [63]. Trust is developed through developing relationships with the clinical team: meeting with the clinicians and staff involved throughout the process of development and integration. Without these relationships, it will be much more difficult to garner trust. This incorporating of different users into the development process will help create a better understanding of how to develop trust at their local sites [6]. Barda et al. emphasize that different needs arise from different clinical stakeholders, especially when considering XAI [3].

3.2.4 Trust Through Augmentation, Not Automation

Different levels of automation and the level of control the operator has impacts trust [31]. Implicit in this agreement from clinicians to the AI development team is that the AI would not be developed to replace them. If the AI developers wanted to replace the clinicians, the clinician likely would not hold that as a positive expectation of the use of AI, nor would this be an ethical, productive endeavor [57]. As Gichoya et al. argue, a more productive focus is upon the clinician-AI team (rather than replacing clinicians) given the complexities of the clinical context [25]. Kiani et al. found that there was an increased performance in the joint teaming of a pathologist and a deep learning-based assistant in the histopathologic classification of liver cancer [36]. Lee et al. found a similar improvement in therapists using AI in a rehabilitative assessment context [41]. Wang et al. found clinicians want to maintain decisional power over the AI and verify any decisions it would make [71]. They also found that clinicians didn’t believe AI could replace them, as one participant stated, “you will have to stay in medical school for 3 years in order to understand this [clinical decision support system].” [71]. Instead, the diagnosis process is a “highly interactive, communicative, and social event”, thus not up for automation anytime soon [71].

To protect autonomy and agency in clinicians, Cai et al. found it crucial to give clinicians tools to refine the system, allowing the clinician to improve the AI, remain in control, and disambiguate mistakes [9]. This is further evidenced by Strohm’s interviews with radiologists regarding AI integration, where radiologists were having to “reframe their professional identity and responsibilities...framing AI applications as “co-pilots” enabling radiologists to perform better while staying in control.” [65]. This is like airplane automation, where pilots need to be trained on how to be better monitors of automation [11]. Clinicians need to be reminded that while they are working in an environment with AI agents, they are responsible for their decisions.

3.2.5 Trust Through a Clinical Champion

Clinical and AI development teams working together are often accompanied by a clinical champion, a key to gaining the positive expectations of the clinical staff [65]. For instance, Lu et al. emphasize the need for a clinical champion, or someone to affirm the clinical utility of the AI system and promote the project within the “complex social hierarchies and regulations... that would be impenetrable to outsiders” [46]. Strohm et al. point out that these insiders share information about AI to other clinicians and promote opportunities for experimentation [65].

3.2.6 Trust Through Clinical Trials and Peer Reviewed Publications

Prior to releasing AI in a clinical workflow, these models need to be evaluated according to rigorous clinical standards [15, 74]. For instance, Sendak’s team had both the sepsis definition and model peer-reviewed and disseminated in clinical and technical venues [22, 23, 45]. Sendak et al. tailored different ways to convey trustworthiness to clinicians depending on what was meaningful to them, using a form of model card and model performance presentations during meetings [52, 63]. Cai et al. also indicate the need for “evidence of FDA approval and published validation in peer-review journals, social endorsement by well-respected medical leaders” [10]. In co-designing a clinical DST, Jacobs et al. found that clinicians would primarily trust the AI based on its validation through randomized controlled trials and endorsement from other clinicians, rather than at different decision points in use [33]. This finding dovetails nicely with recent work deflating the importance of XAI in clinical AI, notably by Ghassemi et al., who advocate more for rigorous external and internal validation of models [24].

3.2.7 Trust Through Public Accountability

A form of public accountability during trial phases can also affect trust. Although seemingly rare in the literature, Sendak et al. offer an account of this [63]. Sendak et al. enabled mechanisms of public accountability by conducting a clinical trial with specified goals and outcomes, combined with an external data safety monitoring board to oversee the safety and efficacy of the system [63]. This enabled positive expectations to be built and exchanges of vulnerability between the clinical and development team.

3.3 Use in context

3.3.1 Trust Through Training and Onboarding Sessions

Training sessions with clinicians also modulate trust: both active training on how to use it and allowing clinicians to test the AI out, understand its limitations, often through onboarding [15, 31, 35]. This onboarding is essential: developers are introducing a sociotechnical system, transforming the complex distributed workflow of clinicians. During initial onboarding and throughout usage, explanations of model predictions, transparency into higher level objectives, global behavior, and tendencies can be needed [10, 31, 62]. First impressions with AI systems greatly influence later trust development [13, 31, 55, 67].

Wang et al. found that a lack of training lessened trust in the AI, as clinicians had to learn alone how to use and understand the system [71]. Henry et al. discuss how in a sepsis alert system, clinicians might dismiss the alert if there aren’t clear signs of sepsis, and the patient has a less common presentation of sepsis [30]. Training clinicians on how the system could detect sepsis despite the typical warning signs would be crucial [30]. This training and onboarding are crucial forms of trust calibration [13].

3.3.2 Trust Through Performance

As clinicians use the AI in practice, their trust will modulate dynamically based on system performance and different sociotechnical factors [31]. The goal is to calibrate appropriate trust in real-time through trust dampening and repair mechanisms to increase human-AI teamwork performance. This is where further investigations of trust in clinical AI are needed: how does trust develop over time in actual usage [35]?

Levy et al. emphasize the importance of long-term investigations of AI's impact on trust [43]. How the AI functions within the workflow has a large impact on trust and reliance. How well does the AI work with live clinical data, in an actual clinical workflow over time? Does the AI miss new edge cases arising within clinical contexts [49]? Was the data used in training similar to how it's gathered in this live clinical context? What unintended consequences arise [8, 66]? How do users accept improper results, lose engagement in the task, or take less initiative [43]?

Given appropriate trust is built upon having knowledge of the AI's performance, it's important to inform clinicians on the AI's past performance [21, 35, 70, 75]. The AI could perform better on certain tasks than others (e.g., diagnosis of different types of lesions) and the clinician would need to adjust their trust as these cases arose [35]. Further, specific environmental contexts can cause the AI to not perform well and reduce trust [35, 42, 58, 71]. For instance, Beede et al. found that poor image quality severely impacted usage of their deep learning system that made assessments based on the image of the eye [4]. How the system responds to such failures can have an effect whether trust is repaired (e.g., how the AI expresses regret) [38].

How are trust dampening and trust repairing mechanisms released as needed, and do they even work as intended [16]? Trust repair would repair trust after a trust violation, while trust dampening would lower expectations as needed [16]. How people respond to different trust repair strategies varies person and context [17, 19]. De Visser argues that designers ought to use different repair strategies for different respective violations and to be mindful of how different contexts and timings affect trust repair strategies [17]. McDermott refers to calibration points, or points in time where AI performance is degraded or improved, and trust needs to be increased or dampened [51]. Through the human-centered design process, designers could know what information the system needs to show at different calibration points (e.g., confidence scores after analyzing an image) [34, 35].

Trust during actual usage will also be influenced by other stakeholders in the clinical team. Clinicians will have varying degrees of experience with the AI: some holding positive expectations, others dismissing the AI because of adverse situations. Each stakeholder will have different predispositions to trusting AI and different levels of meta trust with each other, or: "the trust a person has that the other person's trust in the automation is appropriate" [42]. These networks of trust relations will be impacted by each other [32]. Whether or not a trusted, senior clinician trusts an AI will influence the rest of the team's trust in the AI [28]. Similarly, clinicians may be required to interact with an EHR system more, increasing situational trust [30]. The implementation of AI will have a broader effect on trust between healthcare professionals, and in turn, will affect trust in the AI [59].

3.4 Auditing and monitoring

3.4.1 Trust Through Continual Monitoring

The development team needs to continually monitor performance to ensure the clinical AI is performing effectively [15]. The "you build it, you own it" mentality by Sendak et al. 's team creates positive expectations that the AI will be improved as new information is surfaced based on real clinical data [63]. Medical procedures and best practices are similarly dynamic. Does the AI reflect up to date knowledge of clinical practice [49]? The AI will have systemic, emergent,

impossible to predict effects upon the sociotechnical context of the clinical setting and this needs to be observed continuously [49]. Feedback from clinicians after deployment will be critical to maintaining relationships and maintaining trust [20].

4 CONCLUSION

We need empirical research investigating trust building in clinical AI as it occurs in the wild [63, 73]. In this paper, we outlined several points in which the development, usage, and continual monitoring of a clinical AI project can affect trust. As Chiou and Lee mention, we must go beyond “necessary but insufficient guidelines” that argue for transparency (e.g., “make clear what the system can do”), and instead focus on guidelines for how trust is developed across interactions and situations [1, 13]. Indeed, trust cannot be an afterthought, but rather it must be a central design aim of the project [37]. Future work will more closely examine how each of these points affect trust and how to calibrate appropriate trust at each stage.

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